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Investigating Social Factors Related To the Level of Citizens' Participation with the Police in the Study of Khalkhal City

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Abstract:

This study aimed to assess factors associated with the level of participation of citizens by police, case study: citizens were Khalkhal Framework of the study of the theory of theorists such as Almond and Verba, Ztvmka, and Parsons. . .was presented. This study was a descriptive-analytic survey research in its objective, based on the time period; in terms of relationships between variables are correlational and quantitative assessment techniques. The study population, all citizens 18 to 64 years old Khalkhal city is estimated to number 50,000. In this study, according to the characteristics of the population and much of its population, research and data collection using a sample of 381 residents were selected as sample. In this study, the validity was used to measure reliability of questionnaire was used Cronbach's alpha. Spss software to analyze the data was used. The results showed that the independent variables satisfaction with police performance, the pious people, the political and social trust and the confidence of the dependent variable in partnership with the police, there is a significant relationship. As well as the independent variable economic and social status of respondents with no significant differences in participation with the police.

Keywords: *satisfaction of the police, religious people, social trust, political trust and cooperation with the police*

Introduction and statement of the problem

Participation is one of the words that is not ambiguous in the culture of social sciences, despite its wideness in the conceptual space. In a general definition, participation means collaboration. Participating in a work, task or activity and being present in a group, group and organization for discussion and decision-making, either actively or passively, in which the role and responsibility of the individual is not defined and specified (Mohsani Tabrizi, 1994: 141) .

particular, participation refers to those voluntary activities through which the members of a society participate in the social processes of that society and participate directly and indirectly in shaping social life (ibid.). National development in the third world countries depends more than anything on the active participation and effective social harmony of the people of the society. The absence of this participation and social consensus provides the basis for conflicts and differences and conflicts between the performance of different sectors (private and public) of the society, and a large part of the scarce resources of these countries is spent in fighting against the adverse effects of these encounters. Therefore, the attitude of the planners and the policy of the

editors on the threshold of entering the 21st century should be aimed at increasing the role of people's participation in the progress process, especially in the social, political and economic fields.

With the participation of people in their related work, their ability to innovate and create is increased and it is exploited in a good way. People have dealt with the executive works in a real way and hence their gap with government institutions, local governments and also the conflict of their interests is reduced. The features of participation are: Participation is the right of the people and more than anything, it requires their conscious action. Participation is not an imposed or invited event, but a kind of empowering the powerless groups to play a role in solving their problems, such problems are neither ordered nor imposed, but must be earned, that is, it is not a privilege that the government He gives it to his elements, but it is a right that he should use.

Participation is a process that is constant and ultimately progress.

Participation is a quantitative and qualitative effort and has degrees, so its breadth and depth are variable and important, if the scope of participation is not deep, it becomes vulnerable. Participation has two-way consequences. In order to be effective, it requires fundamental changes in thought and action, which must come from within the society and crystallize in stable forms accepted by the society and the government. The ideas of participation have a common point and that is giving importance to the role and opinion of the people in political decisions and their access to the benefits of power. From the second half of the history of the formation of the police force, due to the changes and social developments that have occurred, police issues need deep understanding, especially the social approach was more and more considered by the high-ranking managers of Naja and this idea Increasingly, it was brought up that one should first know the demands and expectations of the people from the police and then implement police agents and plans.

The issue of social security and cooperation with the police is particularly important in urban society. Today, with the increase of urban communities and their intertwining, the situations of meeting needs and responding to them have become more complex. Knowing and controlling security in cities requires a detailed and all-round look so that it is possible to understand the various dimensions of security and discover the hidden connections between them at various levels (Hedayt and Abbasi, 2009: 178).

The police, the most trusted security force, with its positive performance and by properly addressing its responsibilities, benefits from the sympathy and cooperation of the people and multiplies the ability of its organization in its missions with a community-oriented approach; Because the presence and participation of people and increasing social trust are among the professional requirements of security forces' actions in our society today. In order to achieve such an important goal, creating a culture and implementing plans and programs should be on the agenda of the police.

Therefore, today, the police is one of the important foundations of society and government, which is responsible for order and security in society, and to fulfill its important role, it needs the cooperation and participation of the people, and this work is implemented by receiving trust from the people. Without people's trust in the police, their participation and cooperation is impossible, and in such a situation, security can be established with hard tools and that too in a short and transitory period; Therefore, one of the plans to create a safe environment and establish a sense of security among the people is to gain citizens' trust in the police, as one of the important agents of the government (Shaygan, 2007: 38). On this basis, the constant monitoring of the state of people's trust in the police as one of the indicators of the success of the police, as well as the attitude of the people towards the police and its role in maintaining the security of the society, is an organizational necessity that must be carried out continuously, and the officials and organizational planners from Because of that, they are used in maintaining and increasing trust in the police. Because this trust is hard to get, but it is easily lost with one incident, and when it turns into mistrust, it is very difficult to change it (Koleman, 2017: 260). Therefore,

constant attention to people's attitude will lead to more awareness of the police's performance, prevention of a decrease in people's trust, and finally, an increase in their participation in the police.

Considering the above justifications, the main question of this research is how to access sustainable security with people's participation and benefit from it and citizens' participation in it is effective enough? Today, participation is a major and inseparable indicator of progress, and day by day its importance and necessity is being insisted on more; As stated in the Human Development Report of the United Nations Development Program (1993), the issue of people's participation in social activities is the main issue of our time. Based on this, in the goals of the development strategies, the idea of the active participation of broad sections of the society in political and social decision-making has been insisted. (Azimi Arani, 1994: 52) Therefore, even if an organization is more efficient in its field of activity, it can receive the participation and trust of the people. In addition, it increases trust in agents, trust in the system, participation and legitimacy of the system. Such a system can be the government, the police or any other official or unofficial sphere. It is important for the police to provide and facilitate people's participation. People's participation in supporting and cooperating with the police in various dimensions shows their trust in the police. According to Hashemi (2013: 23), this work is called participatory action and it is found when the police is efficient and receives the trust of the people. In this case, people consider themselves effective and show cooperative behavior. To conduct research on such a topic, the following main goal is sought:

The main purpose of this research is to determine the social factors related to the level of participation of citizens with the police. and the following sub-objectives fulfill the main objective:

Determining the relationship between satisfaction with police performance and the level of participation with the police

Determining the relationship between the level of religiosity of people and the level of participation with the police

Determining the relationship between the level of social trust and the level of participation with the police

Determining the relationship between the level of political trust and the level of participation with the police

Determining the relationship between the respondents' social and economic base and their involvement with the police

Previous researches.

1-Hamid Ansarian (2000) has done a research on people's participation in fulfilling the duties of Faraja. The results of his research have shown that the level of social participation of the respondents is due to their sense of security, satisfaction with the performance of Naja and their level of social trust. In other words, the more the people's sense of security, the higher their satisfaction with the performance of Faraja and the greater the social trust in it, the greater their participation in Faraja activities and cooperation with them.

2-Fariba Shaygan (2007) has conducted a research titled "Investigating the level of people's trust in the police in Tehran" and the results show that the level of trust in the police has been evaluated favorably. In the comparison of the police as one of the important government organizations, there is more hope for the future of the police compared to the five political institutions of the country. The people's trust in the future of the police and the fact that it can solve the problems of the society was more than other institutions, and thus it has won the first rank.

3.Fateme Pashazadeh Azari (2010) conducted a study titled "Investigation of the effect of social factors on the level of political participation of students of Islamic Azad University, Roudhen Branch". The results show that the level of political awareness of students, the social base of students' parents, the level of communication between students with their peers, the level of students' activities in university political organizations, the gender of students, the marital status of students, and the field of study of students have a significant relationship with the political participation of students. In other words, the confirmation of these hypotheses and

the factors of students' use of mass media and students' age have no significant relationship with students' political participation (Pashazadeh, 2009: 73).

4-The results of Abdulmutallab Abdullahzadeh's research (2009). It shows that in the studied population in Tehran, motivations such as increasing national cohesion, following a leadership position, supporting the system of the Islamic Republic of Iran, and a sense of legal responsibility have a significant relationship with electoral participation. In other words, the respondents who voted in most of the elections mentioned the mentioned motivations as the most important reasons for participation. Among the social sources of the study, "adherence to performing Shariah duties", "political trust", "interest in politics", "participatory skills" and "feeling of political effectiveness" show a significant correlation with electoral participation. The "resources" that in the context of Iranian society, unlike most other societies, did not show a significant correlation with participation in elections, were education and income (Abdullah, 2008: 109)

5-Mohsen Palizban (2008) has conducted a research entitled "Investigation of students' willingness to political participation and the factors affecting it". The results of the research indicate that the students' willingness to participate in politics is "low". Based on the statistical analysis, a positive relationship between students' willingness to political participation and their sense of political efficiency, political sensitivity and political awareness has been confirmed. Accordingly, there is no relationship between the socio-economic base of students and their willingness to participate politically (Palizban, 2018: 33).

6-Tawheed Abdi (2007), a research to examine the effect of the implementation of the Faraja social security improvement project on people's trust in the police in the central area of Karaj, which was implemented by the police command of Tehran province in 1386. The purpose of doing it is to provide data about the scope of the effectiveness of this project about the level of people's trust in the police and its reflection in the studied society, reducing crimes, increasing satisfaction with the police, increasing public participation, increasing the authority of the police, increasing the sense of security, the law. The results revealed that there is a significant relationship between the plan to improve social security and people's sense of security, crime reduction, people's satisfaction, people's participation, people's acceptance of the law, and police authority (Abdi et al., 2017). : 261).

7-Zainab Fatemi Amin (2008) has done an article titled "Study of Social and Psychological Factors Affecting the Political Participation of the People of Tehran". Based on the results of the research, it can be said with more than 99% certainty that each of the variables of age, marital status, level of education, religious flexibility, degree of religiosity, satisfaction with life, political freedom, political legitimacy, political trust, political friends, fatalism (fatalism), sense of political efficiency and effectiveness, sense of political powerlessness, political alienation, distribution of responsibility, political family, political awareness, political avoidance, use of media, social trust, satisfaction with the government's performance, the content of candidates' slogans, having free time on election day, Stability in party orientation, the importance of election results, the importance of social monitoring, has a significant relationship and correlation with the level of political participation (Fatemi Amin, 1388: 199).

8-Ali Hossein Hosseinzadeh and Ali Anbari (2010) have conducted a research entitled Sociological explanation of people's trust in the police in dealing with a social issue in Ahvaz city. Trust is the basis and essence of social relations and as the most valuable and important component of social capital, which effort in estimating its amount and increasing it among the people for the police force, considering the breadth and variety of missions, can contribute more.

9-Gol Shiri et al. (2008) conducted a research titled the effect of social cohesion on the participation rate of villagers: a case study of Gandaman district, Borujen city. The results show that there is a positive and significant relationship between social cohesion and the social participation of villagers (Gol Shiri et al. colleagues, 2009: 147).

Theoretical and operational definition of variables you have religion: Theoretical definition:

It is the feeling of belonging to individuals and religious community and their commitment to a particular religion (Demirchi, 2008: 249).

Practical definition: In this research, the variable of religious beliefs is measured with items such as belief in God, the Day of Resurrection, praying and fasting, etc. with a questionnaire and a five-point Likert scale.

Social trust

Theoretical definition:

Expectations and commitments obtained and socially accepted by individuals to organizations and institutions of life are called social trust. (Ezekia, 2001: 138)

Practical definition:

In this research, the variable of social trust is measured with items such as acceptance of government offices, clergy, police force, etc. with a questionnaire and a five-point Likert scale. Trust in officials

Theoretical definition:

the degree of positive and supportive attitude of people towards political institutions and political actors in the society is political trust. Three indicators of trust in the political system, trust in political institutions and trust in political actors are derived from it. (Quoted by Abdullah , 1389, 129)

Practical definition:

In this research, the variable of political trust is measured with items such as trust in government officials, MPs, municipality, etc. with a questionnaire and a five-point Likert scale.

Police performance

Theoretical definition: Police performance is a policing policy strategy that aims to achieve effective and efficient crime control, reduce the fear of crime, improve the quality of life and expand police services by using community resources that reduce crime. The aim of this work is the need for the police to be responsible and the society to participate as much as possible in the decision-making process and to pay more attention to social rights and freedoms.(Trojanorich 2013:29)

Practical definition:

the expansion of public education and police patrols (on foot and on horseback), which greatly affects people's sense of security and participation. The development of hardware and software tools that are considered necessary for police work. Participation

Theoretical definition:

From a sociological point of view, committed participation (the act of participation) and how (participating) are different. Participation in the first meaning is the active participation in the group and has an opinion on the social activity carried out, and in the second meaning, it indicates belonging to a special group and having a share in its existence (Biro, 2010: 275).

Practical definition:

two indicators (proposed by the World Bank, 1999); 1. Preparation for mutual help from the people of the place of residence. 2 is the interest in the participation of the people of the neighborhood to solve its problems. We also follow the above indicators in this research.(Aghili et al. 2018)

Economic-social base

Theoretical definition: It is said that social situations and position that a person obtains in the structure of social rank of a group in comparison with other groups, the social base and position of the person determines the rights and advantages of the person (Vashuqi, Nikkhalkh, 2010: 247; Koen, 2011: 83).

Practical definition:

In this research, the socio-economic base of families in Khalkhal city is measured according to indicators such as the level of education, occupation and income with a questionnaire and a five-point Likert scale.

The theoretical framework of research

Today, participation is viewed as a major indicator of progress, and its importance and necessity are being insisted on more; As stated in the human development report of the United Nations Development Program, the issue of people's participation in social activities is becoming a major issue of our time. On this basis, in the goals of the development strategies, it has been insisted that the active participation of broad sections of the society in political and social decision-making is necessary (Azimi Arani, 2013: 52). The word participation means finding a share in something and benefiting from it, or participating in a group and therefore cooperating with it (Biro, 257: 1374). Participatory social activities are those efforts with which the ordinary citizen exerts influence on policy-making (Niazi, 2002, quoted by Almond and Powell, 1996: 138). Even if an organization is more efficient in its field of endeavor, it can receive the participation and trust of the people. In addition, trust in agents increases trust in the system, participation and legitimacy of the system. Such a system can be the government, the police or any other official or unofficial sphere. This work is very important for the police to provide the ground for people's participation. People's participation in supporting and cooperating with the police in various dimensions shows their trust in the police. This is called participatory action, and it occurs when the police are effective and able to gain public trust. In this case, people consider themselves effective and show cooperative behavior (Hashmi, 2013: 25).

The three foundations of credit, performance and behavior are the first for trust. Trust is based on the many years of experience we have gained. It is possible that we have the experience of dealing directly with some people and based on those experiences, we trust them or lose our trust. Sometimes we have first-hand information about the behavior of some people about other people and we can trust them based on that. Also, our information about trusted people may be second hand. That is, it is based on quotations, documents, evaluations or introduction letters of others (Ztomka, 2005: 82). Regarding trust in the police, according to Zatomka, some may or may not trust the police due to direct contact and interaction with the police and obtaining first-hand information, but most people trust the reputation and credibility of the police with reports, news and the statistics that are obtained (published in this field) and inform the people about the performance of the police; Therefore, if this information is up-to-date and in accordance with reality and positive, it will affect the trust in the police in the society.

Parsons considers trust as a result of the functioning of the political and economic system, trust in the law, trust in government institutions, and the roles of the police and the army (quoted by Hosseinzadeh, 2009). Hess Miller focuses on three specific historical periods in the performance of the police in fulfilling security and believes that three major transformations in their performance have occurred for the formation of police forces in different societies. This transformation of patterns is described as special periods of police performance (Hess and Miller, 2012: 47-43). Therefore, the most important task of the police force and even governments is to fulfill social security. In fact, the principle of the existence of governments and societies was based on the need of people to have security. herefore, the most important task of the police force and even governments is to fulfill social security. In fact, the principle of the existence of governments and societies was based on the need of the people to have security, and if they did not have it, the people did not need to gather and create societies

and give some unlimited powers to the governments for security. Based on this, the more the police succeeds in producing security and maintaining it and receives the trust of the people, the closer it gets to the boundaries of popularity (Abdi, 2012: 39).

According to Erikson, trust is faith and belief. He considers religion to be effective in creating trust and a product of care and compassion (Erikson, 1968:242). Putnam is also one of the thinkers who focuses on the variable of social participation in the context of relationships, social relations, religious beliefs, exchanges between people, social participation in the form of groups and networks, tendencies and action orientations such as general Grai considers social solidarity and collective action to be part of the network of relationships and emphasizes the role of trust and participation. (Piran and others, 2006).

Hypotheses

There is a relationship between satisfaction with police performance and their participation with the police.
There is a relationship between people's religiosity and their involvement with the police.
There is a relationship between the level of social trust and the level of people's participation with the police.
There is a relationship between the level of political trust and the level of public participation with the police.
There is a difference between the social and economic base of the respondents and their involvement with the police.

Research methodology

This research is a survey research, in terms of analytical descriptive purpose, in terms of cross-sectional time, in terms of relationships between variables of correlation type and in terms of quantitative measurement techniques. The statistical population of the present study, all citizens aged 18 to 64 in Khalkhal city, is estimated to be 50,000 people. In the current research, considering the characteristics of the statistical society and its large population, 381 citizens were selected as a sample size to conduct research and collect information using Cochran's formula. It was determined using Cochran's formula ($h=$) as described below.

$$n = \frac{N \cdot t^2 \cdot p \cdot q}{N(d)^2 + t^2 \cdot p \cdot q} = \frac{50000 (1/96)^2 \cdot (0/5)(0/5)}{50000 (0/5)^2 + (1/96)^2 \cdot (0/5)(0/5)} = 381$$

N=50000 (the total number of the statistical population)

d=0.05 (permitted possible error)

t = 1.96 (reliability coefficient that is usually considered in social research)

P = 0.5 (probability of trait)

q = 0.5 (probability of absence of attribute).

In this research, we used face validity. In this regard, the prepared questionnaire was given to a number of expert and selected sociology professors, and their agreement on the indicators is a clear proof of the validity of the designed questionnaire.

The most common method in measuring reliability is using Cronbach's alpha method; Therefore, in this research, we calculated reliability using Cronbach's alpha coefficient for each of the variables.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha N of Items

.859 7

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha N of Items

.914 8

Satisfaction with the performance of police participation

Political trust

.759 7

Reliability Statistics

.894 11

Cronbach's Alpha N of Items

.742 11

Cronbach's Alpha N of Items

.627 6

Social trust

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha N of Items

.894 11

Religious trust

.627 6

We used scientific documents to draw the theoretical framework of the research. A multi-stage cluster sampling method was used to select the respondents. Based on the multi-stage cluster sampling method, Khalkhal city was divided into 5 geographical regions, North, South, East, West, and the center, and in the next stage, blocks were determined as clusters, and then several households were selected within each block and samples were randomly selected from among them.

This research was conducted using a researcher-made questionnaire. The type of questions in the questionnaire was closed and open questions were used only for background variables. After reviewing and ensuring the correctness of the collection method, the research questionnaires were coded and the information of the questionnaires was transferred to the computer in the form of code. The information of the questionnaires was processed in the software (SPSS) in two parts, descriptive and inferential. It was processed in two descriptive and inferential sections.

Hypotheses, tests

There is a relationship between satisfaction with police performance and their involvement with the police. Pearson

There is a relationship between people's religiosity and their involvement with the police. Pearson

There is a relationship between the level of social trust and the level of people's participation with the police. Pearson

There is a relationship between the level of political trust and the level of public participation with the police. Pearson

There is a relationship between the social and economic base of the respondents and their involvement with the police. One-way analysis of variance

Findings

4-2- Descriptive findings.

Table No. (1-4): Distribution of respondents according to gender

Genus	abundance	percentage
Male	206	1/54
Female	175	9/45
Total	381	0/100

According to the data in the table above, 54.1 percent of all respondents were male and had the highest percentage. Also, 45.9% of respondents are female and have the lowest percentage.

4-2-2- Marital status

Table No. (2-4): Distribution of respondents according to marital status

Marital status,	Percentage	Frequency
Single	76	9/19
Married	305	1/80
Total	381	0/100

According to the data in the table above, 19.9 percent of all respondents were single and had the lowest frequency. Also, 80.1% of the respondents are married and have the highest frequency.

4-2-3- Age

Table No. (3-4): Distribution of respondents according to age

Abundance	Percentage	Age
Less than 20 years	35	2/9
30-21 years	216	7/56
40-31 years	89	4/23
50-41 years	35	2/9
More than 51 years	1/6	6
Total	381	0/100

According to the data in the above table, the youngest age was 20 years old and the oldest age was 51 years and older. Most of the respondents are between 30 and 20 years old.

4.2.4 Level of education:

Table No. (4-4): Distribution of respondents according to the level of education

The amount of education, the frequency of percentage

illiterate	36	4/9
Primary	34	9/8
Guidance	35	2/9
Secondary	44	5/11
Diploma		10/2/39
Postgraduate diploma		10/2/39
Bachelor's degree	5/20	78
Master's degree	22	8/5
Total	381	0/100

According to the data in the above table, 20.5% of the respondents in this study were bachelor's level of education and they had the highest frequency, and 5.8% of the respondents were with postgraduate education and they had the lowest frequency.

Table (4-5) descriptive statistics

Variables	mean,	minimum,	maximum
Performance of the police force	0709/26	9	35
Social trust	7795/37	19	55
Political trust	2178/22	8	30
Religious beliefs	39/7244	12	55
Cooperation with the police (affiliated)	40/32	9	3045

According to the data in the table above, it can be said that the variable of police performance averaged 26.07, the variable of social trust averaged 37.77, the variable of political trust averaged 22.22, the variable of religious beliefs averaged 39.72 and the variable of participation with the police averaged 30. They have 32.

4-3- Inferential findings

4-3-1- The first hypothesis

There is a relationship between satisfaction with police performance and their participation with the police. Zero hypotheses: There is no relationship between satisfaction with police performance and their participation with the police.

Counter hypothesis: There is a relationship between satisfaction with police performance and their participation with the police.

Table (6-4): Pearson's correlation test between satisfaction with police performance and their participation with the police

Variable 1, variable 2, Pearson's correlation coefficient value, significant level

Satisfaction with the performance of the police, cooperation with the police, 0.776, 0.000
 According to the data in the table above, it can be seen that the significance level of the test is less than 0.05, so the null hypothesis is rejected and with 95% confidence, it can be said that there is a significant relationship between the two variables under study. Considering the positive sign of the correlation coefficient (0.776), there is a direct relationship between the two variables, that is, with the increase of one, the other also increases.4-3-2- The second hypothesis

There is a relationship between people's religiosity and their involvement with the police. Hypothesis zero: There is no relationship between the level of religiosity of people and the level of their participation with the police.

Counter hypothesis: There is a relationship between people's level of religiosity and their participation with the police.

Table (7-4): Pearson's correlation test between people's level of religiosity and their participation with the police

Variable 1, variable 2, Pearson's correlation coefficient value, significant level

The level of religiosity of people involved with the police is 0.894 0.000

According to the data in the table above, it can be seen that the significance level of the test is 0.000 less than 0.05, so the null hypothesis is rejected and with 95% confidence it can be said that there is a significant relationship between the two variables under study. Considering the positive sign of the correlation coefficient (0.894), there is a direct relationship between the two variables, that is, with the increase of one, the other also increases.4-3-3- The third hypothesis

There is a relationship between the level of social trust and the level of people's participation with the police.
Zero hypothesis: There is no relationship between the level of social trust and the level of people's participation with the police.

Counter hypothesis: There is a relationship between the level of social trust and the level of people's participation with the police.

Table (4-8): Pearson's correlation test between the level of social trust and the level of their participation with the police

Variable 1, variable 2, Pearson's correlation coefficient value, significant level

The level of social trust in cooperation with the police is 0.662 0.000

According to the data in the table above, it can be seen that the significance level of the test is less than 0.05, so the null hypothesis is rejected and with 95% confidence, it can be said that there is a significant relationship between the two variables under study. Considering the positive sign of the correlation coefficient (0.662), there is a direct relationship between the two variables, that is, with the increase of one, the other also increases.4-3-4- The fourth hypothesis

There is a relationship between the level of political trust and the level of public participation with the police.
Zero hypothesis: There is no relationship between the level of political trust and the level of people's participation with the police.

Counter hypothesis: There is a relationship between the level of political trust and the level of people's participation with the police.

Table number (9-4): Pearson's correlation test between the level of political trust and the level of their participation with the police

Variable 1, variable 2, Pearson's correlation coefficient value, significant level

The level of political trust in cooperation with the police

According to the data in the above table, it can be seen that the significance level of the test is less than 0.05, so the null hypothesis is rejected and can be accepted with 95% confidence.

Research Results

The first hypothesis can be analyzed with the theory of Almond and Verba and it is aligned with it. From the point of view of Almond and Powell, social activities are those activities that seek participation by ordinary citizens to influence policy making (Niazi, 2002, quoted by Almond and Powell, 1996: 138). Even if an organization is more efficient in its field of activity, it can receive more people's participation and trust. In

addition to that, trust in agents, trust in the system, participation and increasing the legitimacy of the system. This system can be government, police or any other official or unofficial area. It is important for the police to provide the ground for people's participation. People's participation in supporting and cooperating with the police in various aspects shows their trust in the police. According to Hashemi (2013: 25), this is called cooperative action, and it occurs when the police is efficient and can gain the trust of the people. In this case, people will consider themselves effective. Also, the result of this research is in line with the research of Alireza Jabedar et al. The effect of Public Surveillance Office of Greater Tehran in building trust between the police and the public is the title of a research conducted by Alireza Jabedar and colleagues. One of the ways of forming the role of the people in fulfilling and maintaining security is the participation of citizens in monitoring the performance of the police, which increases the sense of belonging and mental control in citizens, and thus psychological security is guaranteed and the prevalence of abnormality is reduced. (Jebedar et al., 2008: 141). The second hypothesis is in line with Erikson's theory, according to Erikson, trust is caused by faith and belief. He considers religion as a factor and effective in creating trust born of care and compassion (Erikson, 1968:242). Putnam is also one of the thinkers who emphasizes the variable of social participation. He believes that the network of relationships, social communication, religious beliefs, exchanges between people, social participation in the form of groups and networks, tendencies and action orientations such as inclusion Socialism and generalism, social solidarity and collective action are part of the network of relationships and play a fundamental role in creating trust and participation (Piran et al., 2016).

and show cooperative behavior. The third hypothesis is in line with Zatumka's theory, Zatumka has considered three bases of money or credit, implementation or performance and appearance or behavior for primary trust. Trust is the result of many years of experience that we have gained. It is possible that we have had the experience of dealing directly with some people and based on those experiences, we have trusted them or lost our trust. Sometimes we have first-hand information about the behavior of some people towards other people and we can trust those people based on them. Also, our information about trusted people may be second hand. That is, it is based on quotations, documents, evaluations or letters of introduction from others (Ztomka, 2014: 82). Regarding the trust in the police, according to Zatumka's opinion, some may or may not trust the police due to direct contact and interaction with the police and obtaining first-hand information, but most of the people know the image and credibility of the police through reports and news. and get statistics that will be published in this field and inform the public about the performance of the police; Therefore, if this information is up-to-date and in accordance with reality and positive, it will affect the trust in the police in the society. Also, Fariba Shaygan has conducted a research entitled Surveying the level of people's trust in the police in Tehran (Fariba Shaygan, 2007: 166) and the following results have been obtained: The level of trust in the police has been evaluated favorably. In the comparison of the police as one of the important government organizations, there is more hope for the future of the police compared to the five political institutions of the country. The people's trust in the future of the police and that it can solve the problems of the society related to it was more than other institutions, and in this sense, it won the first rank. The fifth hypothesis is in line with Parsons' theory. Parsons considers trust to be dependent on the functioning of the political and economic system, trust in the law, trust in government institutions and the roles of the police and the army (quoted by Hosseinzadeh, 2009).

In relation to the result of this research, a research titled "People's participation in performing the tasks of NAJA" was conducted by Hamid Ansarian in 2019 on the order of NAJA's Social Vice President. The results showed that the level of social participation of the respondents depends on their sense of security, feeling of satisfaction with the performance of Naja and their level of social trust. In other words, the greater the people's sense of security, the higher their satisfaction with the performance of NAJA and the greater the social trust in it, the greater their participation in NAJA activities and cooperation with them (Karamati and Moltaft, 2016: 397). Suggestions

Based on the findings of the research and in order to apply these results and also in order to attract more participation of citizens with the police, the following suggestions will be presented:

1. Efforts should be made to familiarize people with the police and respect the laws, as well as the process of

building trust and cooperation from childhood, or to pay more attention to the issue of legality and cooperation with the police in educational programs and activities of schools, so that it is well institutionalized.

2 Holding classes and meetings with people and local trustees and presenting police programs and functions in order to create and raise the level of people's hope for the future of the police.

3. Due to the significance of the level of religiosity and trust in the police, efforts should be made to inform about the successful and efficient performance of the police through Friday imams and clerics.

4 Efforts to remove the obstacles to people's satisfaction with Faraja and to deal more with people's complaints and requests.

5 Providing the necessary and practical training to the police officers to present a favorable and suitable image of Faraja to the people and to try to improve the level of individual and group abilities and capabilities of the police to increase the level of trust in the police and the future of the force. Also, the use of neat uniforms and clothes and showing a commendable appearance by the police to gain the trust and participation of the people.

6 Availability of the police and timely and quick presence in times of need and emergency, as well as decisively dealing with those who disrupt social order and security to increase the level of people's trust in the police and ultimately increase people's participation with the police.

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